

Dentists on the Frontline : Preventing Hepatitis Transmission in Oral Healthcare

Received on: 25- 05- 2025; Accepted on: 04-06-2025; Published on : 29 07 2025

Sujata Datta¹

Deepthi Jawa²

Shipra Jaidka³

Ashjan Ashraf Batha⁴

Apurva Chadha⁵

Madhuri Gupta⁶

PG Student¹

Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry
Divyajyoti College of Dental Sciences
and Research
Modinagar

Professor²

Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry
Divyajyoti College of Dental Sciences
and Research
Modinagar

Professor & HOD³

Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry
Divyajyoti College of Dental Sciences
and Research
Modinagar

PG Student⁴

Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry
Divyajyoti College of Dental Sciences
and Research
Modinagar

PG Student⁵

Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry
Divyajyoti College of Dental Sciences
and Research
Modinagar

PG Student⁶

Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry
Divyajyoti College of Dental Sciences
and Research
Modinagar

Abstract

Liver disease encompasses a broad spectrum of conditions that impair liver function, including infections, alcohol misuse, drug toxicity, and autoimmune disorders. Hepatitis, a major cause of liver inflammation, has significant global health implications. The five primary hepatitis viruses (A, B, C, D, and E) vary in transmission, pathogenesis, and clinical outcomes. Hepatitis A (HAV), an RNA virus, spreads primarily via the fecal-oral route and is prevalent in regions with poor sanitation. It causes acute liver inflammation but does not lead to chronic disease. Clinical features include fever, jaundice, and abdominal discomfort, with diagnosis confirmed through serologic testing for IgM anti-HAV. Management is supportive, and prevention relies on sanitation and vaccination. Hepatitis B (HBV), a DNA virus, is transmitted through blood and body fluids, including vertical and sexual transmission. HBV poses a high risk of chronic infection, leading to cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. Clinical manifestations range from asymptomatic infection to severe liver disease. Vaccination is the cornerstone of HBV prevention. In dental practice, strict infection control protocols and vaccination of healthcare workers are essential to reduce transmission risks. Post-exposure prophylaxis and appropriate patient management further mitigate the spread of infection in healthcare settings.

Keyword - Dentist, Hepatitis, Liver disease, Oral manifestation.

Introduction

The liver performs a multitude of roles in preserving health and balance. It produces the majority of necessary serum proteins, including albumin, transporter proteins, blood coagulation factors V, VII, IX, and X, prothrombin, and fibrinogen, [in addition to numerous hormone and growth factors], generates bile and its transporters (cholesterol, lecithin, phospholipids, and bile acids), regulates nutrients (glucose, glycogen, lipids, cholesterol, and amino acids), and metabolizes and conjugates lipophilic compounds (bilirubin, cations, and drugs) to aid in their excretion in bile or urine. The metabolism of medicines, lipids, proteins, bilirubin, and hormones is all altered by liver disease.¹

Types of Liver Disease²

Liver disease generally refers to conditions that damage liver. They can develop for many reasons, including:

- Damage from viruses. e.g-Hepatitis
- Alcohol overuse. e.g- Alcohol-related cirrhosis
- Medication misuse.e.g-Drug- induce hepatitis

- Exposure to toxins. e.g- Toxic hepatitis,
- Autoimmune conditions that block the liver's ability to function properly

Experts have identified more than 100 different types of liver disease.

Hepatitis

The inflammation of the liver is known as hepatitis. The illness may resolve on its own or may worsen and lead to liver cancer, cirrhosis, or fibrosis (scarring). Although hepatitis viruses are the most frequent cause of hepatitis worldwide, autoimmune disorders, alcohol, narcotics, and other toxic chemicals can also result in hepatitis.

The five primary forms of hepatitis viruses are A, B, C, D, and E. Because of the burden of disease and mortality they inflict, as well as the possibility of outbreaks and epidemic spread, these five categories are the most concerning. Specifically, types B and C cause

Access this article online

Website : www.updent.in

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14998264>

Quick Response Code

How to cite this article : Datta et al. - Dentists on the Frontline : Preventing Hepatitis Transmission in Oral Healthcare, AJOCD-HT 2025

chronic illness in hundreds of millions of people and are the main cause of cancer and liver cirrhosis together. Viral Hepatitis is one of the major global public health issues, and every year millions of individuals suffer from it. Viral Hepatitis caused 1.34 million fatalities worldwide in 2015, with the majority of viral Hepatitis deaths owing to chronic liver disease or primary liver cancer .

Most cases of hepatitis A and E are brought on by consuming tainted food or water. Parenteral contact with contaminated bodily fluids typically results in the development of hepatitis B, C, and D. Receiving contaminated blood or blood products, invasive medical procedures utilizing contaminated equipment, and sexual contact are common ways for these viruses to spread. Hepatitis B can also spread from mother to kid, from family member to child, and during childbirth.³

Hepatitis A

Hepatitis A is the most commonly reported type of hepatitis in United States. It is caused by hepatitis A virus (HAV) ,which is a small, undeveloped and symmetrical RNA virus. Incubation period for hepatitis A virus is between 3 to 5 weeks with a mean of 28 days. Virus replicate in liver and large quantities are shed in feces up to 1 week prior to onset of symptoms. Unlike hepatitis B and C, hepatitis A does not cause chronic liver disease but it can cause debilitating symptoms and rarely fulminant hepatitis (acute liver failure), which is often fatal.

Epidemiology

Infection is common in low- and middle-income countries with poor sanitary conditions and hygienic practices, and most children (90%) have been infected with the hepatitis A virus before the age of 10 years, most often without symptoms. In middle-income countries and regions where sanitary conditions are variable, children often escape infection in early childhood and reach adulthood without immunity. Infection rates are low in high-income countries with good sanitary and hygienic conditions.³

The WHO estimates that approximately 1.5 million people are infected with HAV each year. With the implementation of vaccination, the incidence of HAV in the United States has significantly decreased. The incidence of acute HAV infection has decreased by 92% from 12 cases per 100,000 in 1995 to 1 case per 100,000 in 2007.⁴

WHO estimates that in 2016, 7134 persons died from hepatitis A worldwide (accounting for 0.5% of the mortality due to viral hepatitis).⁵

Transmission of HAV

Hepatitis A generally spread through fecal oral route (when an unaffected person eats or drinks food contaminated by fecal material of infected person). Blood transfusion is a very rare cause of hepatitis A.⁵

Risk factors for HAV include

- Institutionalization
- Close personal contact
- Travel to a foreign country
- Occupation
- Parenteral drug abuse
- Homosexuality

Pathogenesis

HAV, first identified in 1973 by Feinstone et al., is classified in the family Picornaviridae and genus Hepatovirus. It is a positive-sense, single-stranded RNA virus which replicates primarily within hepatocytes. Animal studies showing HAV antigen in the epithelial cells of intestinal crypts and cells of the lamina propria in the small intestine suggest replication might also occur at these sites. Once ingested orally, the virus is taken up from the gastrointestinal tract and the HAV particles are carried to the basolateral membrane of the hepatocyte via the portal circulation. The hepatocellular injury in acute HAV infection is mediated by various immune mechanisms. It has been shown that patients with acute HAV infection have the virus-specific T-cell mediated release of cytotoxic interferon-gamma. Additionally, recent mice-models have demonstrated HAV-induced hepatocellular apoptosis and inflammation associated with the innate immune response. The humoral immune response is responsible for the diagnostic serologic assays. Following replication in the liver, HAV is excreted in bile and released into the stool. The concentration of the virus is highest in the stool during the 2 weeks before the onset of jaundice, at which point the individual is most infectious. Most people are no longer infectious 1 week after jaundice appears at which time stool shedding and viremia are decreased.⁵

Clinical Sign And Symptoms

1. The clinical manifestations of HAV infection range from asymptomatic infection to acute liver failure, but it does not progress to chronic hepatitis.
2. Development of symptomatic hepatitis is associated with patient age. Relatively few children under 6 years of age (<30%) manifest hepatitis symptoms, whereas the majority of adults (>70%) develop symptoms that persist for 2–8 weeks.
3. The onset of hepatitis A is often abrupt with fever (18%–75%), malaise (52%–91%), nausea or vomiting (26%–87%), abdominal discomfort (37%–65%), and then dark urine (28%–94%) and jaundice. When the patient seeks medical advice, the fever has usually disappeared. On physical examination, hepatomegaly (78%) and jaundice (40%–80%) are frequently detected.⁵
4. Less commonly, pruritus, diarrhea, arthralgia, or skin rash develop.

Diagnosis

1. **Serologic testing** : Acute hepatitis A is diagnosed by serologic testing to detect HAV-specific immunoglobulin (IgM) antibodies in the blood.
2. **Reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction** : This is include to detect the viral RNA. Immunoglobulin G (IgG) anti-HAV emerges soon after infection and remains present for the person's lifetime.
3. **Complete blood count** : Blood work will reveal a mild lymphocytosis and normal prothrombin time. If the prothrombin time is elevated, it should raise suspicion of severe liver damage including risk for encephalopathy.
4. **Liver function test** : Hepatitis A is associated with an elevation in aspartate aminotransferase, which returns to normal in 4–6 months. Bilirubin levels are also elevated and if they persist one should suspect cholestatic liver disease.⁴

Management

1. No specific treatment is needed for most patients with acute, uncomplicated HAV infection beyond supportive care. Complete recovery from symptoms may take several weeks to months. In the rare case of fulminant hepatitis from HAV infection, liver transplantation may be a life-saving measure. Extra hepatic complications are managed routinely.
2. According to the WHO, the most effective way to prevent HAV infection is to improve sanitation, food safety, and immunization practices. In the United States, vaccination against hepatitis A is available as inactivated, single-antigen vaccines (HAVRIX and VAQTA) or in combination with hepatitis B (TWINRIX). The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention recommends vaccination for children 12 months or older, travelers to endemic countries, gays, illegal drug users, individuals with occupational risk exposure, persons with clotting factor disorders or chronic liver disease. Standard adult dosing recommends administration of two doses of the vaccine 6 to 12 months apart. These vaccines are highly efficacious were seroconversion rates approaching 100%.
3. Until more recently, immunoglobulin was the only treatment for post-exposure prophylaxis against HAV. However, animal studies and clinical trials demonstrated the efficacy of post-exposure immunization with an inactivated HAV vaccine has led the CDC to recommend the vaccine instead of immunoglobulin for exposure to HAV in healthy individuals aged 1 to 40 years. For individuals 41 years and older, immunoglobulin administration is preferred due to the risk of more severe clinical presentation and limited evidence of vaccine efficacy in this age group. Children less than 12 months, individuals with chronic liver disease, and immunocompromised persons should also receive immunoglobulin.⁵

Hepatitis B

Hepatitis B is a major global health problem. Hepatitis B is an infection of the liver caused by the hepatitis B virus (HBV). The infection can be acute (short and severe) or chronic (long term). Hepatitis B can cause a chronic infection and puts people at high risk of death from cirrhosis and liver cancer.⁷

Epidemiology

The burden of infection is highest in the WHO Western Pacific Region and the WHO African Region, where 116 million and 81 million people, respectively, are chronically infected.⁷ Sixty million people are infected in the WHO Eastern Mediterranean Region, 18 million in the WHO South-East Asia Region, 14 million in the WHO European Region and 5 million in the WHO Region of the Americas.⁸

In India, HBsAg prevalence among general population ranges from 2% to 8%, placing India in intermediate HBV endemicity zone and the number of HBV carriers is estimated to be 50 million, forming the second largest global pool of chronic HBV infections.

Structure of Hepatitis B Virus (HBV)

HBV is a DNA virus belonging to the family Hepadnaviridae. It is a complex 42 nm double-shelled particle. The outer surface or envelop of the virus contains hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg). It encloses an inner icosahedral 27 nm nucleocapsid (core), which contains hepatitis B core antigen (HBcAg). Inside the core, there is a circular double-stranded DNA and a DNA polymerase.⁹ (Fig:1)

Fig1-Hepatitis B virus structure

Transmission of HBV

Various modes of transmission for chronic HBV (Hepatitis B Virus) infections are:

1. **Mother-to-Child Transmission (Vertical Transmission) :** Most chronic HBV infections in children are acquired through mother-to-child transmission during childbirth or early childhood. This mode of transmission is particularly common in high-prevalence settings where infant vaccination, especially birth-dose vaccination, may be suboptimal.
2. **Sexual Transmission :** HBV can also be transmitted sexually, especially among men who have sex with men (MSM) and individuals engaging in unprotected sex with multiple partners. In the US, nearly 50% of acute HBV infections are associated with sexual activity.
3. **Horizontal Transmission in Early Childhood :** Up to a third of new HBV infections in children could occur through horizontal transmission in early childhood. This includes transmission between children, within households, or within families. This mode of transmission is particularly significant in sub-Saharan Africa and among unvaccinated children who migrate to other regions.⁸
4. **Medical Procedures :** Transmission can also occur through poor infection control and injection safety practices during medical, surgical, and dental procedures.
5. **Traditional Practices :** Certain traditional practices, such as scarification or circumcision, may also contribute to HBV transmission if proper infection control measures are not observed.

Pathogenesis

Pathophysiology involves knowing how the virus enters the body, replicates, and triggers immune responses that lead to liver damage.

1. Viral Entry and Replication

- Hepatitis B virus (HBV) enters the body through contact with infected blood or bodily fluids. This can happen through sexual contact, sharing needles, or from an infected mother to her baby during childbirth.
- Once in the bloodstream, HBV targets liver cells, known as hepatocytes. It binds to specific receptors on the surface of hepatocytes and enters them.
- Inside the hepatocytes, HBV releases its DNA, which is then transported to the nucleus of the cell. Here, the viral

DNA is integrated into the host cell's DNA, becoming a part of the hepatocyte's genetic material.

- The integrated viral DNA serves as a template for the production of new viral particles. These particles are assembled in the cytoplasm of the hepatocyte and then released into the bloodstream.

2. Immune Response

- The body's immune system recognizes the presence of HBV and mounts a response to eliminate the virus. This involves both innate and adaptive immune mechanisms.
- Innate immune cells, such as natural killer cells and macrophages, are activated to destroy infected hepatocytes and inhibit viral replication.
- Adaptive immune responses, involving T cells and B cells, are also activated. Cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTLs) target and kill infected hepatocytes, while B cells produce antibodies against HBV antigens.
- However, HBV has developed strategies to evade the immune system, such as by downregulating antigen expression and altering the presentation of viral antigens to T cells.

3. Liver Damage

- The immune response against HBV, particularly the cytotoxic activity of CTLs, can cause inflammation and damage to hepatocytes.
- Chronic inflammation and hepatocyte damage lead to the development of liver fibrosis, where scar tissue replaces normal liver tissue. Over time, this can progress to cirrhosis, a condition characterized by severe scarring and loss of liver function.
- In some cases, chronic hepatitis B infection can also increase the risk of developing hepatocellular carcinoma (liver cancer).⁸

Clinical Sign And Symptoms

1. Around 30-50% of adults and children develop clinical illness typical of hepatitis B after initial exposure to HBV. The incubation period for hepatitis B usually ranges from 60 to 150 days.¹⁰
2. Early symptoms that occur before jaundice include constitutional symptoms like malaise, fatigue, and anorexia for a period of 1-2 weeks.
3. In the acute phase, the typical clinical signs and symptoms include nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, and jaundice. In some cases, skin rashes, joint pain, and arthritis may occur.
4. Acute hepatitis B progresses to chronic HBV infection in 30-90% of people infected as infants or young children and during adolescence or adulthood around <5% of people infected may develop chronic infection. Chronic infection with HBV results in chronic liver disease, including liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma.⁸

Oral Manifestation

1. Intraorally, the greatest concentration of hepatitis B infection is the gingival sulcus. In addition, periodontal disease, severity of bleeding, and bad oral hygiene were associated with the risk of HBV.

2. In patients with liver disease, the resultant impaired hemostasis can be manifested in the mouth as petechiae or excessive gingival bleeding with minor trauma. This is especially suggestive if it occurs in the absence of inflammation.¹¹

Prevention And Management Of Hepatitis In Dental Clinic^{10,12}

1. Immunization

To decrease the burden of hepatitis in dental health care workers, it is recommended that the dental professionals should receive immunization against hepatitis virus and should use individual protective equipments such as gloves, head caps, masks, etc. Despite the availability and recommendations on hepatitis B vaccination, the vaccination rate among dental professionals has remained consistently low in developing countries.

It has been found that 5–10% of normal subjects do not produce the anti-hepatitis B surface antibody (anti-HBs) after receiving a standard course of HBV vaccine. Thus, a post-vaccination testing, 1–3 months following the third dose of vaccine, is recommended for health care workers who have contact with blood.

2. Exposure that might place a dentist at risk of hepatitis infection includes the following:

- Percutaneous injuries (needlestick or cut with a sharp object).
- Contact with potentially infectious blood, tissues, or other body fluids.
- Mucus membranes of the eye, nose, or mouth or non-intact skin (exposed skin that is chapped, abraded, or afflicted with dermatitis).

3. Guidelines for treating hepatitis patients

- No dental treatment other than urgent care should be rendered for a patient with acute viral hepatitis
- Hepatitis B is of primary concern to the dentist. Individuals still carry the virus up to 3 months after the symptoms have disappeared, so any patient with a recent history of hepatitis B should be treated for dental emergency problems only
- For patient with a past history of hepatitis, consult the physician to determine the type of hepatitis, course and length of the disease, mode of transmission, and any chronic liver disease or viral carrier state
- For recovered HAV or HEV, perform routine periodontal care
- For recovered HBV and HDV, consult with the physician and order HBsAg and HBs laboratory tests. If HBsAg and anti-HBs tests are negative but HBV is suspected, order another HBs determination. Patients who are HBsAg positive are probably infective (chronic carriers); the degree of infectivity is measured by an HBsAg determination. Patients who are anti-HBs positive may be treated routinely. Patients who are HBsAg negative may be treated routinely.

4. Precautions for treating active hepatitis, positive-HBsAg (HBV carrier) status, or positive HCV status:

- Consult the patient's physician regarding status
 - If bleeding is likely during or after treatment, measure prothrombin time (PT) and bleeding time. Hepatitis may alter coagulation; change treatment accordingly
 - All personnel in clinical contact with the patient should use full barrier technique, including masks, gloves, glasses or eye shields, and disposable gowns
 - Use as many disposable covers as possible, covering light handles, drawer handles, and bracket trays. Headrest covers should also be used
 - All disposable items (e.g., gauze, floss, saliva ejectors, masks, gowns, gloves) should be placed in a lined wastebasket. After treatment, these items and all disposable covers should be bagged, labeled, and disposed of, following proper guidelines for bio-hazardous waste
 - Aseptic techniques should be followed at all times. Minimize aerosol production by not using ultrasonic instrumentation, air syringe, or high-speed handpieces. Remember that saliva contains a distillate of the virus. Pre-rinsing with chlorhexidine gluconate for 30 s is highly recommended
 - When the procedure is complete, all equipments should be scrubbed and sterilized. If an item cannot be sterilized or disposed of, it should not be used
 - All working surfaces and environmental surfaces should be wiped with 2% activated glutaraldehyde (Cidex).
- 5. Work practice controls are an important adjunct for preventing blood exposures. They are as follows:**
- Using a one-handed scoop technique, a mechanical device designed for holding the needle cap to facilitate one-handed recapping, or an engineered sharp injury protection device (e.g., needles with re-sheathing mechanisms) for recapping needles between uses and before disposal
 - Not bending or breaking needles before disposal Avoid passing a syringe with an unsheathed needle
 - Removing burs before disassembling the handpiece from the dental unit
 - Using instruments rather than fingers to grasp needles, retract tissue, and load/unload needles and scalpels.
 - Placing used disposable syringes and needles, scalpel blades, and other sharp items in appropriate puncture-resistant containers located as close as feasible to where the items were used
 - Giving verbal announcements when passing sharps
- 6. Post-exposure prophylaxis**
1. Control monitoring- If any of medical staff was exposed to hepatitis, it would be necessary to do control testing for HBV, including mandatory counseling. This considers the following:
 - Testing for anti-HBs antibodies 1–2 months after the last dose of vaccine [anti-HBs antibodies cannot be tested 6–8 weeks after the administration of anti-HBs immunoglobulin (HBIG) because of the possibility for false-positive results]
 - Advising the exposed person not to donate blood, plasma, organs, tissue, sperm, and to abstain from risky behavior
 - Offering the psychological counseling if needed.
 2. Control testing and advising after exposure to HCV include the following
 - Repeat the test for anti-HCV antibodies and ALT at the earliest 4–6 months after exposure.
 - Do the test for HCV RNA for 4–6 weeks for early diagnosis (caution due to the possibility of obtaining false-positive results).
 - During the testing period, the exposed person must not donate blood, plasma, organs, tissue, or sperm .
 - Exposed person should abstain from changes in sexual activity, pregnancy, breastfeeding, or professional activities
 - Counseling Services should be Offered.

Conclusion

Hepatitis, particularly types A and B, presents significant health challenges worldwide, especially in regions with limited healthcare resources. HAV, while generally self-limiting, can lead to serious complications in vulnerable populations, and HBV poses long-term risks due to its chronic nature and potential for oncogenic progression. Dental practitioners play a vital role in recognizing the implications of hepatitis on oral health and ensuring a safe clinical environment through immunization, infection control protocols, and post-exposure management. With proper education, preventive practices, and collaboration with medical professionals, the dental healthcare system can significantly reduce the risk of hepatitis transmission and contribute to overall public health safety.

References

1. Trefts E, Gannon M, Wasserman DH. The liver. *Curr Biol*. 2017 Nov 6;27(21):1147-1151.
2. Mutchler C. Types of Liver Disease and How to Treat Them. *very well health*. 2023 September 16: 1-12.
3. AlShurman M, AlShurman BA, Sehar H, Evans A, Alzoubi T, Mac C, Butt ZA. Uncovering the Underlying Causes of Severe Acute Hepatitis of Unknown Aetiology in Children: A Comprehensive Review. *Dr. Sulaiman Al Habib Medical Journal*. 2023 Dec;5(4):101-117.
4. Gholizadeh O, Akbarzadeh S, Hashemi MG, Gholami M, Amini P, Yekanipour Z, Tabatabaie R, Yasamineh S, Hosseini P, Poortahmasebi V. Hepatitis A: viral structure, classification, life cycle, clinical symptoms, diagnosis error, and vaccination. *The Canadian Journal of Infectious Diseases & Medical Microbiology*. 2023;1-17.
5. Iorio N, John S. Hepatitis A. *StatPearls Publishing*. Jul 2023:1-8.
6. Shin EC, Jeong SH. Natural history, clinical manifestations, and pathogenesis of hepatitis A. *Cold Spring Harbor perspectives in medicine*. 2018 Sep 1;8(9):1-10.
7. World health organization. Hepatitis B. 2024 April 9. <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/9789240091672>.
8. Tripathi N; Mousa YO. Hepatitis B. *StatPearls Publishing*. 2023 July 9:1-7.
9. Dr. S N Chugh, Dr. Anshul Chugh. *Textbook of clinical medicine for dental student*. Arya publication. fourth edition 2016:240-245
10. 52) Gupta P V. *Pediatric dentistry for special child*. JAYPEE publication 1st edition 2016;3.:P.109-217.
11. Gambhir RS. Hepatitis B and C infection: Clinical implications in dental practice. *European Journal of General Dentistry* | Vol. 2013 Jan;2(1):14-19.
12. Dahiya P, Kamal R, Sharma V, Kaur S. "Hepatitis"—Prevention and management in dental practice. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*. 2015 Jan 1;4(1):33-39.